

“SWACCH BHARATH” A Step towards Sustaining Cleanliness - A Case Study of MRPL Mangalore

Pratheeksha

Lecturer in GovindaDasa College, Surathkal and

Research scholar,

Srinivas Institute of management studies,

Srinivas University, Mangalore - India

pratheeksha.anchan@yahoo.com or pratheeksha@gdc.edu.in

&

Dr KVM Varambally

Research professor

Srinivas University, Mangalore

ABSTRACT

Corporate social responsibility is the concept of the day. Modification of Companies' Act 1956 to 2013 has emerged the importance of corporate social responsibility. Companies Act 2013 made it compulsory for the companies to spend 2% of their turnover or profit (with certain categories) on societal well-being. CSR is the responsibility of the organisation to work for the development of the nation through contributing their percentage of profit for the improvement of society and the environment. CSR is not the donation it is one way of doing business and improving organisations image through contributing to education, poverty, SwacchBharath, women empowerment, health and many more. CSR represents the company's norms, values, and principles to society. Because of compulsion by the Government, all the organisations are seriously involved in CSR activities. SwacchBharathAbhiyan is one of the components on CSR. This case study is to analyse the contributions made by the MRPL to CSR in general and SwacchBharath in particular. MRPL is a central public sector organisation, earning huge profits and turnover over a decade. MRPL contributing more towards societal well-being. The study is to examine the impact of CSR and SwacchBharath on sustaining cleanliness in the society and also to identify the progress of CSR activity. The case study is based on secondary data collected from journals, websites, newspaper and informal conversation with the CSR committee head of MRPL.

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility, SwacchBharath, MRPL, Sustaining.

Introduction

CSR was discovered in the United States in 1980 as the notion of corporate personal accountability. The US encountered social and environmental issues during this era owing to the enormous decline in dollar prices which led to the focus on CSR. The duty of the organization is to strive for better culture and environment. Corporate social responsibility for profit and survival, the Organization takes advantage of society and environment, so it is up to the Organization to give it to society. In education, gender equality, poverty, starvation, empowerment of women, hygiene issues, SwacchBharath can contribute their earnings. From 1980 to till today the organisations started to show their responsibilities towards stakeholders – i.e. shareholders, employees, environment, customers and the society as a whole. It is therefore correct for Brownie to say that ‘CSR is the companies ' duty to follow the strategies and to make the choices that favour community and its principles. The provisions of CSR are contained in Clause 135 of company's bill 2012. The Companies bill list the CSR activities in paragraph 135 contains five sub-clause of the CSR Schedule, The primary focus is to build a stronger connection between enterprises and the society, and to improve company perspectives. For some classifications of organization, Clause 135(5) CSR activity is mandatory. For those firms whose net worth of Rs 500 crore or more, turnover of Rs. 1000 crore or more, net gain of Rs. 5 crore or more, CSR activity is obligatory. It is a pride to state that India is the first nation to render CSR operations mandatory in compliance with Section 135 of the Company Act 2013.

CSR models

The evolution and scope of company personal behaviour are described in some models. The model of Carroll's pyramid of CSR is noteworthy.

CSR is described by Archie B. Carroll as the full spectrum of obligations businesses have towards society. A 3-d conceptual business results model has been suggested. Carroll says that a company has four classes of corporate efficiency commitments.

Economic: the company as an economic organization is primarily responsible for the satisfaction and sustainability of the economic requirements of society, excess generation and further extension and diversification to reward investors.

- ✓ Legal: Land regulations and global trade and trade laws are to be respected in accordance with the impact of the organization.

- ✓ Ethical: Ethical obligations are standards that the society expects the company to follow although not codified by legislation. Like not involved in mismanagement.
- ✓ Philanthropic: philanthropic responsibilities refer to the voluntary contribution of company to social well-being such as participation in the growth of a society or in other social initiatives relating to health, hygiene, healthcare, schooling, and mass consciousness.

Debbie haskie (2018) developed a four strategies for the sustainable growth and development of organisation through CSR activities.

1. Develop a vision for society's advantage.
2. CSR vision communication
3. Go to the CSR sight model
4. Crate the dedication of all parties concerned to the vision.

CSR as a business strategy

CSR is, of course, mandated under company law, but beyond this obligation, CSR is a business strategy of one sort that attracts and maintains social perception. To determine their CSR activities level, Andrew (1980) created four issues:

1. Organizational competences determination: what can we do?
2. To analyse the danger and possibilities for businesses: what could we do?
3. Reviewing key implementers ' values: what are we going to do?
4. Social accountability involvement: what should we do?

The organization can be aimed toward fulfilling strategic requirements by identifying the responses to these issues.

History of MRPL

The Assam petroleum company was the monopoly in the country's oil production before independence. After the independence government realized the need to develop oil and gas manufacturing and regarded the emergence of the gas and oil sectors in industrial policy of 1948. The oil manufacturing industry had been in private hands until 1955 and had been associated with the Indian government. At end of 1955, under the governance of Mr K D Malviya, the Minister of Natural Resources took the assistance of the European specialists to explore the prospective oil and to eventually drill operation and was established as a separate department under the Ministry of Natural Resources and Scientific Research.

In 2003, MRPL was acquired by the ONGC (OIL AND NATURAL GAS CORPORATION LIMITED). Mangalore refinery and petrochemical limited (MRPL) is a core public sector

venture under the Ministry of Oil and Natural Gas, located in an enticing area to the north of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka state district(INDIA). In 1988, the MRPL was established. With an initial annual capacity of 3 million tonnes. According to the 2018 report 15 million metric tonne refinery has got a variety design with complex secondary processing system of crudes of various API, delivering varieties of quality products. ONGC is MRPL's parent enterprise. Total Birla group shares and equity capital of Rs. 600 crores were acquired by ONGC on 28 March 2003. MRPL is therefore an ONGC subsidiary with a majority stake. Before the acquisition by ONGC, MRPL was a joint venture oil refinery promoted by M/s Hindustan petroleum corporation limited(HPCL) Now MRPL and ONGC jointly operates OMPL(ONGC MANGALORE PETROCHEMICAL LIMITED). That produces of xylene 1 million tons. In and outside India, the MRPL provides quality products. For centuries, MRPL has been supplying state trading corporation Mauritius with fuel requirements.

A vision to be a world class petrochemical and refining company with a powerful focus on productivity, customer satisfaction, security, health and environmental management, corporate social responsibility and care for employees. with a mission to Energizing sustainability, effectiveness, productivity and innovation leadership, Capitalize on the national and global emerging business possibilities, To cater to the needs of the customers strive, Strong dedication to public welfare sustaining global health, security and environmental standards, Continued concentrate on healthcare and relationships with employees, Imbibe maximum company morality and values norms.

Objective of the case study

- To know the CSR concept and to comprehend the social significance.
- In general, the operations of the CSR in MRPL and the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan programme in particular, to identify the social effect of the MRPL's CSR
- Identifying the evolving Swachh Bharat trend in the MRPL.

Case Methods

Exhaustive literature review regarding the concept and theories has been done through collecting latest Journals from Google Scholar. Secondary data has been collected from various like books, journals, annual report of MRPL, websites of MRPL, magazine, newspapers and informal discussion with CSR committee head of MRPL.

Review of literature

Wood, (1991) argued that CSR is a commitment through social policies and values. The work of CSR is reflected in firms overall performance, this can be assessed by how a firm manages

its social relationship, outcome of CSR Policies and impact of organisation development. Jorge AArevalo, ItziarCastelló, Simone de Colle, Gilbert Lenssen, Kerstin Neumann, Maurizio Zollo(2011) in their study on “Introduction to the special issue: integrating sustainability in business models” reveals that sustainable challenges and development of a organisation can be achieved through CSR .

Amit Kumar Srivastava, GayatriNegi, Vipul Mishra, ShraddhaPandey (2012) in their study “Corporate Social Responsibility: A Case Study Of TATA Group,” Explains how an awareness of social responsibility in companies (CSR) is established, and how it can be examined through the case study conducted by the TATA Group under Mr. Ratan Tata, who demonstrated accountability for raising crowds and protecting the atmosphere and growth of the country

Sinha Sanchali, Dr. Panda Abhaya Kumar(2018)in their study on” Corporate Social Responsibility in India” explains that CSR activities are still evolving in India, Indian companies designed by keeping in view of education, environment, health and safety, rural development through dedicated efforts.

MRPL & CSR

“To be a world-class Refining and Petrochemicals Company, with a strong emphasis on Productivity, Customer Satisfaction, Safety, Health and Environment Management, Corporate Social Responsibility and Care for Employees”.

The CSR activities of the Company are under the "Samrakshan" brand title, which reflects the purpose and engagement of the Company's CSR strategy: to "safeguard, maintain and support" the social, cultural and environmental legacy and the assets of its companies and the nation's sustainable development.

Ensuring an enhanced involvement at all stages of the organisation, while acknowledging the interests of all its players and managing its activities economically, socially and environmentally sustainable. To take up programs that benefit communities in and around their premises with unique regard and commitment to the poorer segment of community to strengthen the standard of living & social well-being of local individuals. To build a favorable socially responsible image of the company as a corporation by its CSR projects, it has a strong view for MRPL, said by MRPL President D.K Sarraf.

Analysis of various CSR activities under the brand name “Samrakshan”

ShikshaSamrakshan

Shikshasamrakshna's idea of the MRPL CSR operation must be used for education. Bundle of clothes were given to the learners in need, the books and the cupboard were supplied for the government school, computer lab has been built, training courses for young people in rural areas were carried out and self-development programs conducted, midday meal to 400 learners in the rural area. Rangamandira building, a multipurpose spastic physiotherapy vehicle, classroom construction, revamping of the top roof of the Govt School, scientific lab building, auditorium and restore, computer equipping, building of special lion school, infrastructure advancement of government schools and colleges, etc.

ArogyaSamarakshan

The system is centered on the provision of health advantages to the society by constructing free primary health centres, school toilet blocks, a medical camp, financial aid for the poor, The test of physical equipment, infrastructure and other health facilities for the hospitals concerned, eye donation awareness camp, the organization of a artificial limb camp, the proving of physical equipment for physically challenged and/or spasticized persons/ endosufline persons, together with a district health officer Mangalore.

Bhaujansamrakshan

Under the BhaujanSamrakshan concept of CSR, it contributes for the overall development of the society by keeping in mind all the people of the society. Conducted 6 months fashion designer training to the girls of rural area, funding has been done for the construction of community meeting hall, constructed bath cum toilets for Ramakrishna mission boys hostel. Construction of roads, support to backward community entrepreneur, Modification and painting of community hall, construction of retention wall for the road, provided sports equipment, construction of library, construction of veterinary hospital, construction of roofing for community hall, contribution to army fund, infrastructure development of SC/ST community area, procurement of furniture for ashakirana HIV affected children care centre.

Sanskrithisamrakshan

CSR activity of the MRPL contributed for the culture and beliefs of the local area by providing Funding and furniture to temple and daivastana, promotion of local cultural art yakshagana through all India Radio, provided plastic chairs to SC/ST community daivastana.

PrakruthiSamrakshan

Environmental safety is most important element; it's the duty of every individual must contribute for the natural environmental safety. MRPL has undertaken the responsibility of garden maintenance at Mangaluru. The major activity of the MRPL through CSR activity is

to contribute for the SwacchBharathAbhiyan , under this concept various programmes have been conducted such as cleanlinessaround Surathkal area, SwchathaPakwada programme, construction of toilets etc.

From past 5 last year tremendous activities have been undertaken regarding SwacchBharth, the major SwacchBharath activities are construction of sewage treatment plant, construction of individual toilets, toilets for schools and colleges and public toilets, beautification of Surathkal flyover area under the programme of SwacchSurathkal, distribution of waste disposal machine, distribution of napkin burner machine, beach cleaning, SwacchBharathPakwada,Swachata hi seva, providing pure drinking water facility, contribution to relief fund for rehabilitation in kodagu, restoration and development of lakes , provided free LPG kit to BPL cardholder under the concept of smoke free village, solar projects, construction and beautification of bus stop, beautification of compound walls through verliart and beautiful paintings and many more.

This case study is mainly based on **SWACCH BHARATH ABHIYAN**of MRPL on CSR activity head. The study concentrated on the analysis of the activities conducted under SwacchBharath and the amount spent by the organisation over five years.

Journey of SwacchBharathAbhiyan

SwacchBharath mission is a nationwide campaign with slogan” one step towards cleanliness” in India, aims to clean up the street, roads and to develop the infrastructure of the country. Honourable Prime Minister NarendraModi launched this abhiyan on 2 October 2014 in RajGhat. And aims to achieve the mission by 2nd October 2019 on the 150th birthday of Mahatma Gandhi.through ensuring cleanliness and sanitation (solid and liquid waste management and making gram panchayats open defecation-free).Mahatma Gandhi dream is to make India aClean country. In this regard he said that “Sanitation is more important than Independence”. To fulfil the dream of clean India,NarendraModi started a mission called “SWACCH BHARATH ABHIYAN.”

“Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is a clean India Abhiyan.” explains that it is very much required for the people in India to really get the feeling of physical, mental, social and intellectualwell-being.Overall scheme to make India, clean India has been discussed. Vishwakarma, D(2016).Situation analysis with Swacch Bharath to determine the SWOT , financing is the key strength and opportunity for waste management. Jangra B et al (2016) there are an increase of number of toilet construction, in 2014-15, 0.49 to 6.9 in 2017-18 in the rural areas report given by India Brand Equity Foundation.

Table showing the average net profit and amount of CSR activity for the past 5 years:

(2 % on average net profit of 3 years will be utilised in the next financial year, based on that criteria table has been prepared)

Years	PBT(in crores)	Average PBT of preceding 3 financial year)	CSR budget(2% of NP preceding 3 financial years)
2011-12	1320.20		
2012-13	(476.85)		4.65
2013-14	409.70	417.68	3.47
2014-15	(2155.89)	nil	8.36
2015-16	1173.53	nil	Nil (4.04 carry forward from 2014-15)
2016-17	5531	1516.28	5
2017-18	3349.75	3352.86	30.32
2018-19			67.06

Source: Annual Report of MRPL.

MRPL ltd PBT with average PBT of preceding 3 financial years exhibited in the above table projecting a clear vision towards CSR budget to the extent of 2 % of the same. The budgeted amount spent by the company as per the proposed proposal in the current financial year and subsequent years.

CSR activities by MRPL before the introduction of Companies Act 2013

Before the compulsion by Companies Act 2013, MRPL was actively contributed for the development of societal wellbeing through CSR activities. Such as construction of Anganavadi building, infrastructure to the schools, equipments to government hospital in the year 2007, 12 lakh worth equipments were donated to government lady goschen hospital in the year 2008. various modern teaching aid has been provided to government schools of Dakshina Kannada, community awareness programme on environmental protection awareness to the Balagramapanchayath and in government school, contributed 50 lakhs to chief minister flood relief fund and in addition to that MRPL employees also contributed their one day salary amounted to Rs. 11.43 lakhs for this purpose, repairing of water dam, provided infrastructure facilities to SC/ST communities in the year 2009. A substantial budget of Rs. 10 crore has been spent during the year 2009-10. construction of class rooms, scholarship to students, construction of community hall etc during the year 2012 and started

construction of separate block for lady goschen hospital, which was 162 years old and spent 21 crores for the purpose in the year 2012-13 and more.

By the analysis of various CSR activities conducted by MRPL before the introduction of companies Act 2013, Compulsion by the Companies Act does not result in CSR activities conducted in MRPL. MRPL has a concern towards societal well-being from the beginning of MRPL. More than mandatory they are doing it as a responsibility and care towards society and nation development.

Table showing the five years Swachh Bharath activity list and Investment on Swachh Bharath Abhiyan

Activities	2014-15 (lakh)	2015-16 (lakh)	2016-17 (lakh)	2017-18 (lakh)	2018-19 (lakh)	Total
Construction and maintenance of Toilets and sanitation at different schools and colleges in and around the premises.	21.5	153.62	76.48	532.34	892.38	1651.32
Garden Maintenance at Custom House, Mangalore	3.5					3.5
Installation of napkin vending and destroyer machine at various schools of Dakshinakannada ,yadgiri and raichur district of Karnataka.					442.35	442.35
Smoke free village: under this concept free LPG kit connection is provided at jokkaattevillage, chelairu, soorninje			10.26		12	22.26
Drinking water facility through installation of water purifier to various schools and colleges, neighbouring areas and to Bar associations Badravathi.					118.82	118.82
Financial assistance for Swachh Mangaluru Abhiyaan by Ramakrishna Mission.		14.00	50.00	264.74	554.07	882.81
Support to Matha Amrithanandamayi Mutt Mangalore.			10.00	7.08	43.09	60.17
CSR activity at Jokatte Grama Panchayat-Retention wall.			14.00			14
Construction of Sewage treatment plant for educational institute at Vivekananda College, Puttur.				57.25		57.25
Beach cleaning in association with				0.59	0.59	1.18

Department of Forest, Ecology and Environment						
'Swachhatha Hi Sewa' Campaign as per the Ministry Letter, Swachhatha Hi Seva - 16/09/2018 to 02/10/2018				4.53	17.41	21.94
Swachh Surathkal- Beautification of Surathkal Flyover under Swachh Bharath Abhiyaan Program.				5.78	0.66	6.44
Installation of Bio Gas Plant in 29 Hostels in Dakshina Kannada District.				14.82		14.82
Swachh Bharath Pakhwada Programme as per Ministry directive, Swachh Bharath Pakhwada -01/07/2018 to 15/07/2018, 16/08/2018 to 31/08/2018				11.93	20.22	32.15
Swachh Bharath Abhiyaan in Association with Vyakthi Vikasa Trust (Art of Living)- Distribution of Waste Disposal Machine					48.69	48.69
Contribution to Swachh Kosh					200.00	200
Construction of Overhead tank in around refinery					70.80	70.80
Contribution to Karnataka Chief Minister Relief Fund- Rebuilding of Kodagu District					100	100
Restoration and Development of lakes in Dakshina Kannada District					141.60	141.60
Solar project at Schools and colleges					126.85	126.85

Source: annual report of MRPL.

Analysis

Out of 110.74 crores of CSR budget of 5 years, 40.17 crores has been utilised for Swachh Bharath Abhiyan programmes from past 5 years. It's a remarkable contribution made by MRPL a step towards sustaining cleanliness.

Among the activities are undertaken under Swachh Bharath Abhiyan by MRPL, the following activities are highly appreciated by the Beneficiaries.

- The case study found that, under the concept of CSR, MRPL more focused on Swachh Bharath Abhiyan, through this concept various programmes have been conducted, they have concentrated more on construction of toilets, maintenance of toilets to contribute for the hygiene factor. They contributed more amounts for this

purpose. Their intension is to have toilets for each house of backward community and to maintain hygiene in schools and colleges.

- CSR activities has also given importance to women health and hygiene, they have provided napkin vending machine and napkin burner machine to various schools and colleges in rural areas, they invested 442.35 lakh on this purpose.
- Ramakrishna mission Mangaluru is making remarkable activities under SwachhBharathAbhiyana, MRPL providing financial assistance from past 4 years. Ramakrishna mutt undertakes the cleaning activities every Sunday in different areas of Mangaluru. MRPL spent 881.82 lakh for this purpose in past 4 years. And also assisting to mathaamruthanadamayi mutt regarding SwachhBharth.
- SwachhBharathPawaada and Swachatha hi Sewa is the unique programme by MRPL, according to this concept, one week continuous Swachathaprogrammes were conducted in different places by creating awareness through street plays, rallies, vanamahostava, beach cleaning, various competitions in schools and colleges relating to cleanliness etc. from past 2 years MRPL is involved in such activities and 54.09 lakh were utilised.
- Under the scheme of smoke free village, free LPG kit were distributed to the backward communities in the rural areas and spent 22.26 lakh on this regard.
- Pure drinking water facilities have been provided in different schools and rural areas and spent 118.82 in this regard.
- It's remarkable to note that all the CSR activities are funded directly to the source and not by agency middleman.
- It's true that after the compulsion by companies Act, the amount spent on CSR activity has been increased, but it is important to note that before the companies act 2013 also MRPL had contributed to the societal wellbeing in crores.

Conclusions

It is apparent that a thorough thinking and wise action on CSR is required to bring back and maintain the overall stability in the social and economic field. Every company owes some obligation for all human, physical and natural resources to community, the nation and the globe in particular. Taking into account long-term growth and sustainable development, the creation and effective implementation of new policies according to the CSR standards, it is inevitable that a balance can be struck among the global business and society.

As for the MRPL, its mission and accountability towards community and the country have been long accomplished. CSR operations are the driving force behind society's sustainable

growth. Different welfare operations lead to social welfare. MRPL has dedicated a considerable amount to attaining Mahatma Gandhi's vision of 'clean India' by means of the Swachh Bharath scheme. In almost all the schools and colleges and rural regions around Dakshinakannada District, the MRPL contributes to the preservation of sanitation and sustainable hygiene development and cleanliness MRPL strives for the cleanliness aid.

Reference

1. Amit Kumar Srivastava, Gayatri Negi, Vipul Mishra, Shraddha Pandey (2012) Corporate Social Responsibility: A Case Study Of TATA Group, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSRJBM)* ISSN: 2278-487X Volume 3, Issue 5 (Sep,-Oct. 2012), PP 17-27 www.iosrjournals.org
2. Annual report of MRPL for the year 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14, 2014-15, 2015-16, 2016-17, 2017-18, 2018-19
3. Andrews, Kenneth R, *The Concept of Corporate Strategy* (Homewood, IL: Dow Jones-Irwin, 1971)
4. Arevalo, J., Castelló, I., de Colle, S., Lenssen, G., Neumann, K. and Zollo, M. (2011), "Introduction to the special issue: integrating sustainability in business models", *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 30 No. 10, pp. 941-954. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621711111>
5. Archie B. Carroll (2016) "Carroll's pyramid of CSR: taking another look" *international journal of corporate social responsibility article 35*
6. Archie B. Carroll, *The pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the moral management of organizational stakeholders*, from *Business Horizons*, July-August 1991, The Foundation for the School of Business at Indiana University . <http://www.cba.ua.edu/~aturner/MGT341/MGT341%20Readings/Pyramid.pdf>
7. Debbie Haskie-Leventhal, "strategic corporate social responsibility: tools and theories for responsible management" (sage 2018)
8. Jangra B et al. (2016) Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (clean India mission): SWOT analysis *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, Vol 3, Issue 12 Page 3285-3290.

9. Sinha Sanchali, Dr. Panda AbhayaKumar(2018) ” Corporate Social Responsibility in India” *ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research* Volume : 8, Issue : 4,pp 97-106.Online ISSN : 2249-8826.
10. Vishwakarma, D. (2016). Swachhbharatabhiyan clean India abhiyan. *International Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 48-52. Retrieved from <https://sloap.org/journals/index.php/irjmis/article/view/353>
11. Wood D. (1991) Towards improving social performance, world business council for sustainable development*business horizon*vol 34 No.4, pp.66-73
12. <https://www.ongcindia.com/wps/wcm/connect/en/home>
13. <https://www.mrpl.co.in/csr>